

Theoretical Calculation of Activation Energies of Some Sn² Reactions

Malaybikas Pahari and Rama Basu

Theoretical calculation of activation energy for the reactions of chloride and bromide ions with chloro and bromo succinic acid shows that contrary to previous belief these reactions proceed with activation energies (in the range of 25–38 K.cal) in the gas phase comparable to those in solution. Further the reaction with neutral atom is expected to proceed with very low activation energy.

Abundant examples are known in organic chemistry of the reactions of alkyl halides with negative halogen ions. It has been pointed out by Ingold^{1,2} that majority of these reactions proceeds through a bimolecular mechanism in which the negative ion approaches the positive end of the carbon halogen dipole leading to optical inversion if the carbon atom is asymmetric. It likewise appears that this approach will be most probable along the line joining the carbon halogen nuclei.

It has been suggested that these reactions are strongly influenced by the dielectric constant of the medium and solvation of the ions, and carbon-halogen dipole plays the major part in determining the activation energy of these reactions. Taking the various complicating solvent solute interactions into account Ogg and Polanyi³ succeeded in calculating the activation energies for a number of negative ion reactions which were in reasonable agreement with the experimental values. They concluded that these reactions will proceed with reasonable speed if the ions are solvated. This obviously means that the gas phase reaction will proceed with extremely large activation energy. Unfortunately no experimental data for the gas phase reactions are available nor any theoretical calculation has been reported. The object of the present investigation was to calculate the activation energy for gas phase reactions and see how they compare with the experimental values in solution.

Method of calculation : The calculation of the absolute value of activation energy cannot be accomplished even now, nearly thirty years after the theoretical basis was laid down by Eyring and Polanyi⁴. Consequently we will follow the approximate procedure of Eyring and calculate various Coulomb and resonance terms appearing in the theory from the experimental data on molecular spectroscopy.

1. E. D. Hughes, C. K. Ingold and C. S. Patel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **1**, 526.
2. C. K. Ingold and E. D. Hughes, *Nature*, 1933, **132**, 933.
3. R. A. Ogg and M. Polanyi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 604.
4. H. Eyring and M. Polanyi, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, **12B**, 279.

Evaluation of Bond energy : The polyatomic molecules XCRR' and ZCRR' are treated as essentially diatomic, i.e., the centres X, CRR' and Z are regarded as rigid with respect to extension of the linkages. We effectively consider the reaction to be a three-centre three-electron system in a line and calculate the binding energy using the Morse potential function for a diatomic molecule. The binding energy W is obtained as a function of internuclear separations. The method has been described in detail by previous workers⁵.

Evaluation of bond-ion interaction terms : The above estimation of covalent binding energy refers to neutral system. When one of the centres carries a negative charge additional terms will appear in the energy expression due to ion-dipole and ion-induced dipole interactions. The total energy of the system therefore takes the form

$$E(r) = W(r) + \frac{\epsilon\mu \cos \theta}{r^2} + \frac{\alpha\epsilon}{r^4}$$

where r = distance between ion and the dipole at the activated stage, $W(r)$ = Bond energy, μ = Dipole moment of the bond broken, $\cos \theta = 1$, since the path of reaction is linear, ϵ = Electronic charge, α = Polarizability of the bond broken.

RESULTS

Calculations were made for the reaction of chloride and bromide ions with 1-chloro and 1-bromo succinic acid. The constants for Morse potential used in the present calculation are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Constants for Morse potential curve

Bond	D k.cal/mole	r_e (10^{-2} cm)	ω_s cm^{-1}
C-Br	63.3 ^{a*}	1.91 ^{b*}	557 ^a
C-Cl	78.6 ^a	1.76 ^b	665 ^a
Cl-Br	52.12 ^{c*}	2.14 ^b	430 ^c
Cl-Cl	57.08 ^c	1.99 ^b	564.9 ^c
Br-Br	45.4 ^c	2.28 ^b	323.2 ^c

^{a*} = C. E. Sun and C. Liu, *J. Chim. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 98.

^{b*} = Tables of interatomic distances and configuration in molecules and ions; Special publication No. 11, London.

^c = The Chemical Society, Burlington House, W.1 (1958).

^{c*} = G. Herzberg. Molecular spectra and molecular Structure; Spectra of Di-atomic Molecules; 1950, D. Van Nostrand Company Inc., U.S.A.

5. R. Basu and P. Sen, *Nat. Inst. Sci. (India)*, 1967, **33A**, 196.

The dipole moment and polarizability data for C-Cl and C-Br bonds are summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

Dipole moment and polarizability of C-Br and C-Cl Bond.

Bond	$\frac{[b]}{\mu}$ (Debye)	$\alpha[a]$ (c.c.)
C-Br	2.04	3.712×10^{-24}
C-Cl	2.05	2.587×10^{-24}

[a] : $P = \frac{4}{3} \pi N \alpha$, where P is molar polarization.

P is 6.53 C. C for C-Cl and 9.37 C. C for C-Br.

[b] : Y. K. Syrkin and M. E. Dyatkina. Structure of Molecules and the Chemical Bond, London, 1950, Butterworths Scientific Publications.

The activation energy was estimated from the position of the Saddle point in the two dimensional potential energy surface. One such surface is reproduced in Fig. 1. In the Table III are summarized the geometry and energy of the various systems in the transition

state. The total activation energy as apportioned between bond energy, ion-dipole energy and ion induced dipole energy are also given in Table III. In the last column are given the experimental activation energies.

It may be observed that for reaction of bromo succinic acid with bromide ion and chloro succinic acid with chloride ion, the calculated and experimental activation energies are in good agreement with each other keeping in mind the uncertainties in the parameters used in Morse potential function. The fact that the calculated value refer to gas phase reaction and the experimental value to reactions in solutions, the good agreement between theoretical and experimental value suggests that solution does not affect the activation energy for the first two reactions. This should be so since the initial state is $\text{RR}'\text{R}''\text{C}-\text{Br}+\text{Br}^-$ or $\text{RR}'\text{R}''\text{C}-\text{Cl}+\text{Cl}^-$ and the final state is $\text{RR}'\text{R}''\text{C}-\text{Br}+\text{Br}^-$ or $\text{RR}'\text{R}''\text{C}-\text{Cl}+\text{Cl}^-$ and the net change in solvation energy is zero. This situation is not realised in the case of reaction of chloro succinic acid with bromide ion or bromo succinic acid with chloride ion, and the calculated (gas phase) activation energies are much higher than the experimental values. The fact that the calculated activation energies for the two reactions are almost equal as is the case with experimental values, suggests that $S_{\text{Br}}-S_{\text{Cl}} = S_{\text{C-Br}}-S_{\text{C-Cl}}$, where S_x refers to solvation energy for the species X. This may be possible to subject this relation to experimental test.

The present theoretical analysis shows that the negative ion reaction is not expected to proceed with extremely high activation energy. In actual practice such a gas phase reaction may not be realised because of the difficulty of getting a negative ion in the gas phase. Once the negative ion is formed, the subsequent reaction will proceed with a reasonable activation energy. The generation of negative ion by electron impact method has opened up a way for testing the theoretical conclusion.

TABLE III

Reactions	$r_1(\text{\AA})$	$r_2(\text{\AA})$	Bond-energy (k. cal)	Ion dipole energy (k. cal)	Ion induced dipole energy (k. cal)	Total	
						Calc.	Exp.
1. 1-bromo succinic acid + Br^- → <i>d</i> -bromo succinic acid + Br^-	2.83	1.95	4	12.41	9.54	25.95	21.8
2. 1-chloro succinic acid + Cl^- → <i>d</i> -chloro succinic acid + Cl^-	2.80	1.75	4	14.28	8.71	26.99	24.7
3. 1-chloro succinic acid + Br^- → <i>d</i> -bromo succinic acid + Cl^-	2.80	1.95	18.5	12.62	6.81	37.93	23.5
4. 1-bromo succinic acid + Cl^- → <i>d</i> -chloro succinic acid + Br^-	2.76	1.75	11.0	14.39	12.82	38.21	23.6

From the Table III it may be observed that activation energy is determined mainly by the ion-dipole and ion induced dipole interaction, the bond energy part making only a small contribution. We may conclude that neutral atom Sn^2 reaction should proceed with

rather low activation energy. There is atleast one experimental data available which appears to substantiate this expectation. It has been shown by Ogg and Polanyi⁶ that the reaction

proceeds with an activation energy in the range of 8–13 k.cal/mole while the corresponding reaction with iodide ion in solution has a much higher activation energy (above 25 k.cal/mole.)

Department of Chemistry,
Calcutta University,
Calcutta-9.

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6. K. A. Ogg and M. Polanyi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 482.